

New Oxygen Heterocyclics from *Derris scandens* and *Mundulea suberosa*

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Chemical investigation of the roots of *Derris scandens* and the bark of *Mundulea suberosa* revealed the presence of several oxygen heterocyclics such as flavonoids, isoflavonoids, 3-aryl-4-hydroxy coumarins, rotenoids and styryl α -pyrones. For the first time 3-aryl-4-hydroxy coumarins were isolated as natural products from *D. scandens* and *D. Robusta*. The occurrence of 3-aryl-4-hydroxy coumarins along with closely related isoflavones is of biogenetic significance. The hypothetical biogenetic pathway for the formation of the coumarins from isoflavones or its derivatives is discussed.

M. suberosa roots obtained from Coimbatore yielded a new styryl- α -pyrone, whose structure has been assigned on the basis of chemical and spectral evidence. The natural products isolated from these plants are feebly toxic to fish.

Derris scandens is a climbing shrub occurring in India, in Ceylon and in some parts of America. The roots of the plant is known to possess insecticidal properties although not as good as those of *Derris elliptica*. Clark¹ first investigated the roots and isolated a compound named as scandenin, together with lonchocarpic acid and robustic acid. Lonchocarpic acid was previously obtained by Jones^{2,3} from an unnamed species of Lonchocarpus of Venezuela origin. Robustic acid was earlier isolated by Krishna and Ghose⁴ from *Derris robusta* and was subsequently examined by Harper⁵. Krishna and Ghose⁴ while making a survey of the rotenone bearing plants of India, examined the roots of *D. scandens* obtained from Chanda district (Maharashtra) and isolated two crystalline substances which were different from rotenone. Subba Rao and Seshadri⁶ investigated the roots obtained from Chanda and isolated scandenin and two new compounds—chandinin and nallanin.

The close similarity of scandenin, lonchocarpic acid and robustic acid was studied by Subba Rao, Murti and Seshadri⁷. They also showed that in all these compounds the acidic nature was not due to carboxyl group but was due to an acidic hydroxyl group. Lonchocarpic acid and scandenin were known to be isomers, with molecular formulae $C_{26}H_{26}O_6$, and that they formed isomeric dimethyl ethers and diacetates. Both the compounds formed tetrahydro derivatives indicating the presence of two

easily reducible double bonds⁷. Lonchocarpic acid⁸ as well as scandenin⁷ on hydrogen peroxide oxidation furnished *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid. These compounds did not give any colour reaction indicative of rotenoids,¹ flavones or isoflavones.

In 1964 Ollis *et al*^{8,9} investigated the structure of robustic acid. On the basis of physical and chemical evidence, a 3-aryl-4-hydroxy coumarin structure was assigned to robustic acid. Pelter *et al*¹⁰ also confirmed the structure of robustic acid (I) on independent lines. It is the first instance wherein a 3-aryl-4-hydroxy coumarin ring system is found in nature.

In view of the close relationship of scandenin and lonchocarpic acid with robustic acid, it was suggested to us that the former compounds also may belong to this new group. Prof. W. D. Ollis also suggested this possibility at the International symposium on natural products held at Kyoto, Japan (1964). Scandenin and Lonchocarpic acid may possess an additionally, γ -dimethyl allyl substituent on a robustic acid type of skeleton. Thus a partial structure (II) could be considered for scandenin and lonchocarpic acid.

One key reaction which helped us to establish their structures is the identity of alkaline degradation product of scandenin methyl ether (VI) and the methyl ether of the alkaline degradation product of lonchocarpic acid methyl ether (VIII) with osajetin dimethyl ether (VI) and trimethyl ether (VIII) respectively¹¹. Since these alkaline degradation products could not be induced to crystallization, their 2:4-dinitrophenyl hydrazones were compared. Osajetin dimethyl ether was obtained on alkaline hydrolysis of osajin dimethyl ether, an isoflavone procured through

the courtesy of Prof. M. L. Wolfrom. Osajin (III) was isolated from *Maclura pomifera* which belongs to Moraceae¹². Thus it was shown that scandenin and lonchocarpic acid could be represented by (IV) and (V) respectively.

Pelter *et al*¹³ independently established the structures of scandenin and lonchocarpic acid by physical and chemical evidence. The methods we adopted to determine their structures (indicated here) are essentially complementary to those of Pelter *et al*.

More recently two varieties of *Derris scandens*—one obtained from Chanda and the other from Warangal, Andhra Pradesh, have been examined^{14,15,16} in detail. In addition to the major constituents, scandenin and lonchocarpic acid, three new isoflavones and a 3-aryl-4-hydroxy coumarin were isolated making use of modern chromatographic techniques. Structure determination also became easy with the isolation of a number of closely related products from a single plant material. The application of modern physical methods helped considerably in elucidating their structures. The structures of the new isoflavones—warangalone (IX), chandalone (XI), nallanin (XII), and 3-aryl-4-hydroxy coumarin, lonchocarpenin (X) are shown in the chart. The variety from which these are isolated are also indicated. These structures reveal that all the compounds are closely related.

isomeric in nature but their methyl ethers were not identical.

The nmr spectrum of warangalone revealed the four aromatic protons, of A_2B_2 system and their chemical shifts demanded that they may be placed on ring B with phenolic hydroxyl at 4'. On biogenetic considerations, 2, 2-dimethyl chromene oxygen was placed at position 7, and two structures (III) and (IX) were considered initially. Since the former structure was given for osajin it could be excluded.

Osajin (III) on treatment with acid underwent transformation to (XIII), whereas warangalone was unaffected under similar conditions. Therefore the structure (IX) was assigned to warangalone and this was fully confirmed by the alkaline hydrolysis of warangalone dimethyl ether to the deoxybenzoin (XIV) which was cyclised to the ketone (XV).

The isoflavones and 3-aryl-4-hydroxy coumarins were readily distinguished by their UV and IR spectra. While 3-aryl-4-hydroxy coumarins exhibit characteristic coumarin type carbonyl, $\nu_{C=O}$ 1700-1705 cm^{-1} , the isoflavones had their isoflavone carbonyl in the region, $\nu_{C=O}$ 1616-1630 cm^{-1} . In nmr spectra, warangalone and chandalone showed low field singlets in the region δ 7.90-7.80, highly characteristic of 2H-protons of isoflavones.

That both warangalone and chandalone possess 2, 2-dimethyl chromene and γ , γ -dimethyl allyl residues a chelated and non-chelated phenolic hydroxyl groups is readily recognized by nmr and high resolution mass spectrometry. In fact, they were

The structure of lonchocarpenin was established by one key reaction: The reaction of deoxybenzoin (XIV) with methoxycarbonyl chloride provided a 4-hydroxy-3-aryl-coumarin identical with lonchocarpenin (X) in all respects.

Chandalone, although possesses four aromatic protons, as revealed by nmr spectrum, three protons constituted an ABX system plus a singlet. The singlet seemed to be characteristic of 8H-proton of isoflavones. Thus the structure (XI) was assigned to chandalone. This was confirmed by its acid catalysed isomerisation, giving a 2,2-dimethyl chroman (XVI) which on alkaline hydrogen peroxide oxidation gave an acid, $C_{12}H_{14}O_3$. This acid was shown to be identical with 2,2-dimethyl chroman-6-carboxylic acid (XVII), previously obtained during the investigation of the well known antibiotic, novobiocin¹⁷ (XVIII).

Nallanin isolated in the original investigation⁶ of Subba Rao et al⁶ was available. Nallanin, $C_{26}H_{26}O_8$, was found to contain the methoxyl group and a non chelated hydroxyl group. Hydrogen peroxide oxidation of nallanin furnished *p*-hydroxy benzoic acid, indicating the nature of the side phenyl group. Nallanin on methylation provided a monomethyl⁷ ether which was found to be identical in all respects with osajin dimethyl ether. Thus the structure of nallanin was shown to be (XII).

Pelter et al¹⁴ in their investigation on *D. scandens* roots obtained from North India, isolated three minor constituents—scandenone, scandinone and osajin, in addition to scandenin and lonchocarpic acid. Scandenone and warangalone (IX) have identical structures and we preferred the latter name. Similarly nallanin (XII) and scandinone have identical structures and in view of the precedence in isolation,

the former name may be retained. While Pelter et al¹⁴ reported that scandinone has m.p. 207-210°, nallanin melted at 216-17°. The difference may be due to double melting points which is common in these compounds.

The isoflavones and 3-aryl-4-hydroxycoumarins isolated from *Derris scandens*¹⁵ and also from *D. robusta*⁹ show considerable similarity and suggest a common biogenetic pathway leading to these two ring systems. The main sequence of biogenetic pathway leading to the formation of isoflavones have been investigated by Greisebach and his colleagues¹⁸. It seems likely that 3-aryl-4-hydroxy coumarins arise by bio-oxidative transformation of isoflavones, through radical intermediates or $+OH$ as intermediates.

Chemical components of *Mundulea suberosa*

The genus *Mundulea*, which also belongs to Leguminosae, is a well known fish-poison and a poison for crocodiles as well. It is a stout, erect shrub to a moderate size tree with thick corky bark grown in South India, Ceylon, Madagascar and tropical Africa. Worsely¹⁹ reported the presence of rotenone (XIX) and other rotenoids deguelin (XXI), tephrosin (XX) and dehydrorotenone from *M. suberosa* roots of East African origin. From the leaves, obtained from Coimbatore, Subba Rao²⁰ isolated a colourless alkaloid and a flavonol, isorhamnetin. During 1960's the roots of *M. suberosa* were investigated in detail in our laboratories, by Dutta et al., and Ollis et al. *Mundulea sericea*, of East African origin, which was

investigated by Ollis et al is considered by botanists as synonymous to *M. suberosa*. Several isoflavones, flavones and new rotenoids were isolated from this plant. Their structures and the origin of plant material are shown in the chart.

demethylation with aluminium chloride in benzene gave normundulea lactone (OH at 4-position of mundulea lactone) which is easily soluble in 3% sodium bicarbonate solution. The acidic property of this substance appeared to be due to an enolic hydroxy

Region from which
M. suberosa roots
collected.

Reference

STRUCTURE OF THE COMPOUNDS

Maharashtra
Coimbatore
Hyderabad

Dutta et al²¹
Subba Rao et al²²
Subba Rao et al²³

East Africa
Maharashtra
Hyderabad

Ollis et al²⁶
Dutta et al²⁷
Subba Rao et al²⁸

East Africa
Coimbatore

Ollis et al^{29,30}
Subba Rao et al²³

*Structure determination by Venkata Raman et al²⁴ and Ollis et al²⁵.

Mundulea lactone $C_{19}H_{20}O_3$, M^+ 296 was isolated from Coimbatore variety. Its uv and ir data is strikingly similar to those of naturally occurring styryl- α -pyrones—dehydro kawain, methysticin and yangonin³³. The presence of two double bonds is indicated by catalytic hydrogenation, which led to the formation of tetrahydro derivative. Mundulea lactone on rather than a carboxylic group. Its acidic nature

is reminiscent of 4-hydroxy-coumarins and 4-hydroxy- α -pyrones. On alkaline degradation of mundulea lactone, cinnamic acid was obtained while, potassium permanganate oxidation gave benzoic acid. The presence of α , α -dimethylallyl unit at position 3—was deduced from nmr spectrum of mundulea lactone. Thus its structure was established as shown in the chart.

LEASERONE

East Africa

Ollis et al²⁰

MUNDUSERONE
(ROTENOID)

East Africa

Ollis et al^{31, 32}

SERMUNDONE
(ROTENOID)

East Africa

Ollis et al³⁰

MUNDULEA LACTONE

Coimbatore¹

Subba Rao et al²³

Most of the natural products isolated in course of our investigation from *D. scandens* and *M. suberosa* were tested for their fish-toxicity³⁴ taking rotenone as standard with a view to evaluate their insecticidal activity. These compounds are comparatively less toxic than rotenone.

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